

Religious Rebels against Western and Industrial Medicine

*Sketch of an Evolutionary,
Comparative and Global
Approach*

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Kleidung wider den Tod zu Rom. Anno 1656.
Also gehen die Doctores Medici dāhē zu Rom, wann sie die ander Pest erbrunche
sonen besuchen, sie zu curiren und fragen, sich wider den Gift, zu sichern, ein langes Kleid von ge
wartem Tuch ihn Angesicht ist verlarvt, siu den Augen haben sie grosse Crystalline Brillen, wider
Naseneinen langen Schnabel willwolreichende Spreereij, in der Hände welche mit Hand schühser
wol versehen ist, eine lange Lütthe und darmit deuten sie, was man thun, und gebrauchte soll.

1) 'NUEVA JERUSALÉN' DEFIES THE 'VIRUS OF FEAR':

In the past March and April 2020, the little village of Nueva Jerusalén, in Turicato (State of Michoacan), has deeply shocked the Mexican public opinion. This is because the religious leadership of this strange, neo-mediaeval and integralistic fortress, intended to disrespect the Quarantine decreed by the health officials. In the wake of the epidemic of Covid-19, the rulers of this self-proclaimed Sacred City planned to hold mass events of its peculiar Cult of Atonement (for the sins of the unbeliever and lost Modern World), without complying to the official rules of Social Distancing issued by the Federal Mexican Government.

Made up of traditionalist rebels, anti-modern, and anti-liberal peasant and aborigines, direct descendants of the ancient and fierce Cristeros, this Community proclaimed itself since its creation in 1973 (*) as an independent religious republic, rejecting all forms of human or secular government. And ruled only by the sacred will of its tutelary goddess (the Virgen del Rosario), revealed to his self-appointed prophetesses and priests. Because of this seditious attitude, this small city has always been under a sneak attack by the michoacan and mexican media, which disqualifies its inhabitants as a backwards ('rezagados') gang of dangerous religious fanatics...

Actually, the civilian authorities and security forces keep them permanently surrounded by a string of armed troops. And to make matters worse, a certain minority of members of the community itself, deemed to be dissidents (and who for many years were severely repressed and mistreated by their theocratic leadership), are also enthusiastically collaborating with this constant campaign of harassment by the civil or secular powers.

This combined pressure has finally become unbearable. The little holy city had been finally forced to obey the orders of the secular government, allowing the Michoacan health authorities to disinfect its temples. This operation, performed in front of the press cameras, has been a huge affront to a traditionalist movement like this, that was created to restore the totalitarian and violent domination of the Tridentine catholicism. And which declares, as an article of its faith, that all the science and technology of modern urban society is purely diabolic, or enemy of divinity. As it was argued by the most anti-liberals among the Catholic Popes of the past.

 ...

En la comunidad de la Nueva Jerusalén, muebles y espacios públicos fueron sanitizados para evitar cualquier riesgo de contagio de COVID-19. Esta labor se está realizando en todos los municipios del estado mediante el trabajo coordinado de gobierno del estado y la federación.

 53 1 comentario Compartido 12 veces

 Compartir

At Operativo en Nueva Jerusalén, para evitar eventos masivos

Left, Source: <https://archive.fo/dbKF0> - Right, Source: <http://archive.fo/gGBc1>

2) THE CRUSHING DEFEAT OF THIS BESIEGED FORTRESS:

For the first time in its history, the walled fortress, that is the Hermitage 'Nueva Jerusalén', has been physically defeated and isolated. In other times, both the police and the military would have avoided going into it, when there was an armed guard ready to defend the community to the death, from the ungodly world outside. On the contrary, in this year of 2020, the authorities have blocked all its accesses with armed checkpoints, preventing the arrival of buses carrying thousands of pilgrims. These believers, indigenous people, peasants and migrants in the north and the rest of Mexico, very poor and mostly illiterate, or non-Spanish speakers, come at Easter, Christmas and other important dates of the traditional Catholic liturgical calendar, to obtain the healing and miraculous protection of the Virgin of the Rosary. The famous apparition that took place on this hill of Puruarán, to an old peasant woman, sympathetic to the ancient anti-liberal and anti-modern cause of the Cristeros.

In interior of the building of this community we can find thousands of votive offerings, testifying to the gratitude of the believers for these miraculous gifts. But there shall be no miracles this year. The new technology of the drones had allowed to observe within the Hermitage, with its few streets totally deserted. The old peasant fighters against the modern, liberal state, once so dangerous and defiant, now remain secluded in the Community and frightened, desperately praying to the Queen of this little utopian or millennial republic. And hoping that these ominous times will pass, and that the prophecies which have promised them the catastrophic end of the modern urban world, their Satanic Enemy, and the arrival of the Heavenly Court on Earth, shall be fulfilled at last.

Gobierno de Michoacán

FERVOR POLÍTICO

Habltantes de la Nueva Jerusalén asistieron al mitn que encabezó ayer en Turicato el candidato del PRI y el PVEM al gobierno de Michoacán, Ascensión Ortuosa Bárcenas, quien ofreció "diálogo" para atender las problemáticas que co registron al Interior de la comunidad religiosa ■ Foto Ignacio Juárez

3) THE FREEDOM TO PRACTICE A TRADITIONALIST RELIGION, TRAMPLED UPON BY HEALTH AUTHORITIES AND NATION-STATES:

The devotees of the Nueva Jerusalén (we called them also Naborites, as they are followers of the rebel Priest who founded this Hermit, Nabor Cárdenas Mejorada) are only a radical minority within the Catholic world, not recognized or supported by Rome, but execrated as deviationist, for its rejection of the modernization of the Church, since Vatican Council II. They are only a minority of destitute and marginalized peasants, migrants and indigenous people, deeply attached to the rural traditions of folk Catholicism. Treated as ignorant lowlifes, and enemies of progress, they had always been denied the right to speak out freely, in mass media totally adverse to them. They have not been able to express their belief that they have the full miraculous protection of their Queen, so they were not afraid of what they called 'the Virus of Fear'. And that they refused to admit that the government limited their freedom to practice their religious collective rites. Which are necessarily incompatible with the rules of 'healthy distance' imposed by the secular powers.

It is not the first, but it is the biggest defeat that this radical and nativist Catholic movement has suffered at the hands of the modern Mexican liberal state, counting on the complicity of the Catholic Church itself. We suspect that it may mark the beginning of the definitive decline of this radical nativist stream of Mexican folk religion, that is has only survived until now, thanks to the financial support of thousands of pilgrims from all over the region and even from the North and the Philippines. But now the modern secular state has shown that it can interrupt that flow of visitors whenever it sees fit. Once again, we see how the culture of the neocolonial or imperial Mexican capital, led by elites of European origin, crushes the resistance of the local, rural and indigenous communities, which strives strenuously to preserve its traditional identity.

4) THE REVOLT OF TRADITIONAL RELIGIONS AND CULTURES AGAINST THE SECULAR STATE, AND THE WESTERN OR GLOBAL CULTURE:

The Nueva Jerusalén is not an isolated or rare case in the world. On the contrary, many such movements and communities around the globe have rebelled against the imposition of quarantine in the face of the COVID-19, or Sars-Coronavirus epidemic. They have considered it a very serious attack against the free exercise of their beliefs, against their conception of the world, their collective identity and their way of life. Because not all human cultures simply accept the authority of Western (medical) science and the biopolitical diktat of the modern states. On the contrary, many insist on defending traditional or ancestral modes of organization, which predate the industrial and urban culture that the West has imposed by blood and fire on the world. First in the form of colonial oppression, and today through its enormous technological and economic power.

These communities continue to cling to ways of living and thinking that are incompatible with the materialistic utilitarianism of the Industrial Culture, and with the naturalistic or Western scientific and rationalistic world view. They strive to adhere to their own ancestral conceptions of reality, in which mysteries, spirits and/or gods, are still living and acting forces. And only magic or traditional practical religion, i.e., the Wisdom of the local community, transmitted by their forefathers, is effective and beneficial in controlling them. Contrary, for instance, to the politically harmful effects of the products of the monopolistic Western pharmaceutical industry, or to the dependence of the nation-state, the western churches, or any other foreign and hostile powers. What we see here is a clear expression of the radical confrontation that exists between the Folk Community, traditional and local, and its Nemesis: the Global Industrial and Urban Culture. Which has been imposed by force, in the last two centuries, on a multitude of peoples throughout the world, by the Euro-American imperialist powers, and by the suffocating weight of the capitalistic market.

WITCH-DOCTOR IN HIS WIZARD PANOPLY

In Liberia's forest-choked interior the witch-doctor and medicine-man wield considerable influence among certain tribes. One of their duties consists in administering poison to suspected evil-doers and giving judgement according to its effects

5) IN THE BEGINNING, WERE THE HEALERS:

Long before the modern western medical science of the industrial age came to be, it was originally the local religious specialist -the Holy Men of the various cultures- who cared for the lives of the members of the ancient and traditional community (folk), in the face of illness, the misfortune and various deadly dangers. But actually, such specialists were only representatives, that carried out this work always counting on the active cooperation of the whole community, which constantly elaborated, applied, strengthened and re-elaborated its main collective possession: its Theory of the World and of itself. The Healing was mainly done in common here. And it was above all psychological, emotional and intellectual. It consisted of an effort of reconciliation and acceptance of the Existence, accompanying those who suffered in a supportive way, cohering, integrating and giving meaning to their experiences.

Hence the original meaning of the word Religion, i.e., Re-Unification: it is the collective or communitarian experience, in ancient and local societies, of a system of symbolic representation of reality and existence. This world view amounted to to a powerful Collective Mind. A shared discourse and thought, which was expressed performatively in the practice of collective rituals, or rites of passage. That shared Wisdom unified, and gave full meaning, to every act and experience of the people, who felt themselves first and foremost as part of a Collective Subject. A 'WE', a socio-ethnic and ethnolinguistic or cultural identity. This psychic activity allowed the whole society to face the problems of its existence in a cohesive way, unifying its agency or capacity for action. By making existence fully Sacred -shared- or poetic -Meaningful or transcendent-, they succeeded in strengthening the feeling of integration of humans into their collectivity, and into the natural world around them.

6) HOW RELIGION LOST ITS BIOPOWER, OR THE DESACRALIZATION AND DEHUMANIZATION OF HEALING:

The most complex Religious Systems, emerged in the urban cultures or civilizations of the past (in the Hellenistic world, in the Abrahamic, Hindustani or Sinic tradition...) were those that made possible the appearance of our current disciplines of knowledge, developing the ancient sacred language into increasingly abstract and complex conceptual tools, into Philosophy and Scientific Theory. Where the imperial religions had gained more political power, and created large educational institutions, these forms of knowledge specialized. And stimulated by the demand for practical solutions by the urban, economic and political elites, they became radically empirical and materialistic, in search of greater practical effectiveness. They evolved into what we call today 'the Science'.

On the other hand, the growing complexity of the internal organization of these urban and imperial societies disintegrated them into a set of different and competing powers, engaged to this day in an increasingly violent competition. From the 18th century onwards, the ancient political-religious systems lost then its unifying societal role, in favour of the secular nation-states and the industry and market elites.

This is how was born in the West the present Global Urban Mass Culture, deeply alienated from human and environmental reality. An uncohesive, unsupportive crowd, composed of isolated EGOS, unable to communicate between themselves. Without collective power, whose existence is focused on mere subsistence. Who suffers the deepest alienation, loneliness and schizophrenia, due to their inability to find a transcendent, poetic, communitarian meaning to their existence.

It is an increasingly sick society, which is razing the entire fabric of life on Earth, and therefore is rushing towards its self-destruction. In this Brave New World, which is anything but Happy, the treatments of diseases offered by the industrial system had also become the opposite of what the sacred Healing represented, in ancient and traditional communities. For all their technical sophistication, they are just no more than sophisticated palliatives. A way of uselessly prolonging the suffering generated by a more and more dehumanized way of life.

7) REBELS AGAINST THE WESTERN DISENCHANTMENT OF THE WORLD AND THE HUMAN LIFE:

During the present pandemics, the main religious groups in the world today, and those most identified with the global urban and industrial culture, absolutely abide by the quarantine imposed by the international health authorities. Such is the case of Latin Christians -both Romanists and traditional Protestants- and Orientals; liberal Judaism; Hinduism and Buddhism, and, above all, Islam. As well as many other minor but important currents. These are the most universalised and rationalised religious systems, the same ones that made the emergence of scientific medicine possible.

On the other hand, in Mesoamerica, except in the urban world and among the most educated layers of the population, traditional healers of all kinds and Santería from the cult to the Christ of Chalma, up to Santa Muerte, continue to prevail in the widest popular sectors. Indigenous communities have closed in on themselves (eg, Chiapas, among the descendants of the Mayans), reinforcing the power of their leaderships and traditional political-religious systems, prohibiting all outsiders from entering the communities, especially state agents or health officials. The same can be said of the interior of our African continent, where the most magical and traditional healing methods continue to prevail.

Alfredo Gutierrez da Gracias al Señor de Chalma porque le dio una fuerte de arrea y se le iso tarde para yegar a su trabajo como mesero en uno de los restaurantes de las Torres Gemelas de Nueva York y asi poderse salvar de morir. 11 Sep 2001.

But the main insurgents against the authority of modern medical science during this New Plague have been communities who hold a world view not naturalistic, but supernatural or spiritualistic, and who do not accept the Western concept of disease or cure, because their methods of healing are strictly based in the cohesive participation of the community, through the ritual practice:

- In the first place the Integralist Christians, (hostile to liberalism and modern culture, and supporters of some form of theocracy), both traditionalist Catholics, and the most radical fundamentalist evangelicals. Especially in the USA, Brazil or Guatemala.

- And secondly, and in particular, the 'God-fearing' Jews or Haredim, also called ultra-Orthodox. The latter are enormously combative against quarantine and its rules, and their confrontation with the authorities and the security forces has become enormously violent in the state of Israel and on the East Coast of the USA. It is impossible for them to abide by the authority of any secular power, because all their loyalty is due to their own political-religious leaderships, the advice of rabbis who guide them in following the Torah or sacred law.

LIVE from Life Tabernacle Church · March 17, 2020

8) THIS IS NOT -STILL- THE END OF THE GLOBAL HUMAN CULTURAL EVOLUTION:

The disenchanting and mechanistic form of medicine that has been imposed on us continues to leave a large part of society deeply unsatisfied. The medical industry and health authorities suffer a serious credibility crisis, which fuels large movements of dissent, seeking ethical and psychologically satisfying alternatives. Sometimes resorting to the contributions of other cultures, with their healers, magic remedies, miracle cures or diets, or forms of mystical physiology, purification rituals, etc. Other currents rise up in a form of desperate and chaotic rebellion against modern science and technology, which they consider destructive, sometimes resorting to elaborating Lullite-type legends, such as those of the antivaxxers, or the one that blames this Covid virus on the latest technologies, such as the repeaters of 5G connection, which are suffering all kinds of attacks during this pandemic.

But among all these trends, perhaps the most influential is our growing awareness that it has been the Global Ecological Crisis that has made this catastrophic epidemic scenario possible. And this due to the conjunction of the effects of Climate Change, and the Zoonosis that has produced the devastating pressure that human action is exerting on the natural systems of the entire planet. These are profound ills that pose challenges to the very survival of the species as a whole, and that cannot be expected to be faced with mere chemical palliatives, which is the only thing that industrial medicine of the western type can provide us. We therefore need to develop a new type of Global Healing, which is necessary to cure the pathologies suffered by the entire Biosphere and the human population. Including the sick and violent relationships, of fierce competition, domination and dependence, that exist between our different cultures, and that are our main collective problem.

Sources of the Images:

P 1, Cover: German engraving of Doctor Schnabel (i.e. Dr Beak), a plague doctor in Rome in 1656, published by Paul Fürst, ca. 1656. Source: <https://tinyurl.com/w8yjgpp>

(* See our previous work on this subject: <https://tinyurl.com/ybov88vf>

P 2: Ramparts and main entrance to the Fortress of the Nueva Jerusalén de Turicato, Michocán. Picture by Alan Ortega, 2012. Source: <https://archive.fo/RaZVg>

P 3: Facebook Screen Caption. Sanitization in Nueva Jerusalem. April, 15, 2020. Source: <https://archive.fo/4eMe2>

P 4: Pictures: Left, Source: <https://archive.fo/dbKF0> - Right, Source: <http://archive.fo/gGBc1>

P 5: Pictures: Left, Source: <https://archive.fo/KAGvi> - Right, Source: Journal Jornada de Michoacán, 2015, May 23, p 6.

P 6: Ancient Picture of a traditional Medicine-Man, Liberia, Western Africa. Source: <https://archive.fo/HTFV5>

P 7: Manipulation of the world of Spirits and/or Natural Forces by 'shamanic' specialists (South New Wales). Source: <https://archive.fo/r5VSq>

P 8: Images, traditional vs naturalistic and modern ways of treatment of the Illness:

Top: Exorcism and/or spiritual healing, practiced by clerics ordained by the modern imperialist christian churches. Source: <https://archive.fo/5PMDj>

Bottom: Photograph of 17th-century plague doctor mask from Austria or Germany on display in Berlin's. Deutsches Historisches Museum. Source: <https://tinyurl.com/w8yjgpp>

P 9: Images of the evolution of the modern western medicine:

Left: Man in plague mask on Poveglia, ca. 1899. Source: <https://tinyurl.com/w8yjgpp>

Right: Industrial Medicine. Source: <https://archive.fo/eCBMJ>

P 10: Top, Left: Urbi et Orbi. Square of Saint Peter, Rome, empty because of the Pandemics. Source: <https://archive.fo/9bwwl>

Top, Right: Empty Holy Shrine of the Qaaba, Mecca, amidst the covid 19 pandemics. Source: <https://archive.fo/igKye>

Bottom: Mesoamerican Votive Offerin to the Black Christ (actually, the christianization of the nahuatl and precolonial divinity Tezcatlipoca, Smoking Mirror, or Lord of the Night) of Chalma for his supernatural protection. Source: <https://archive.fo/olpak>

P 11: Images of the protests of traditional religious communities:

Top: Pentecostal Christians resisting authorities orders to close their churches. Source: <https://archive.vn/a5CvT>

Bottom: Violent clashes between Israeli police and Haredim, opposing orthodox neighborhoods lockdown. Source: <https://archive.fo/qWbDn>

P 12: Top: Communications masts attacked by conspiracy believers in theories linking 5G to coronavirus. Source: <https://archive.vn/c9Ohr>

Bottom: Graphic Representation of Global Ecological Crisis. Source: <https://archive.fo/21VeR>